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“Sport, Physical Activity and Health: Contemporary Perspectives”**

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finally affects organization's members and their motivation and loyalty towards the sports organization they belong to. References: Bartoluci, M., Škorić, S., (2009.), Menadžment u sportu, Zagreb, Kineziološki fakultet. Erhardt, N., Carlos, M. R., Heckscher, C., (2016) Am I doing the right thing? Unpacking workplace rituals as mechanisms for strong organizational culture, International Journal of Hospitality Management Vol.59, pp.31-41. Janićijević N. (2013) Organizaciona kultura i menadžment, CID, Ekonomski fakultet, Beograd. Kastratović, E. (2004), Osnove menadžmenta sa menadžmentom u sportu, Beograd, Institut za razvoj malih i srednjih preduzeća. Northouse G. P., (2008) Liderstvo: teorija i praksa, Data Status, Beograd.

PUTTING IN PLACE THE FIRST GOVERNMENT'S NATIONAL STRATEGIC PLAN FOR SPORT IN KOSOVO 2017-2021

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Introduction: The purpose of project was to build the 2017-2021 Strategic Plan for Sport in the Republic of Kosovo (first ever Government's Sport Strategic Plan). To support the vision and Sport system, enhancing the inspiration by Gold Medals in Judo for all. Methods: Cooperation with KOS NOC Strategic Plan 2015-2020, was synergic for the methodology and the outcomes of the Strategic Plan methodology paving implementations steps, with the overall information from the meetings organized with sport stakeholders. Results: One of the main objectives of the sports development strategy 2017 -2021 is for the Sport department to change its form of management and to help in organizing the financing of the Sport federations on an annual basis and not anymore on an ad-hoc, project-oriented basis. The current results are: [1] As per 2017-2021 Strategic Plan, Legal Framework completed with several laws, rules and regulations on sponsorship, against violence, sports categorisation, etc. [2] Infrastructure concrete investments in sport stadiums meeting international standards, etc. Discussion: The new strategy of sports in Kosovo should be oriented towards the athletes and citizens that are dealing with physical activity. The period for the implementation of the strategy (Alaj, 2016) for sport will include a wide range of changes in legislative and financial system of sport in the Republic of Kosovo. References: Aćimović, D., Špirtović, O., Jonić, Z. & Projević, A. (2013). Act.in Phy.Ed.and, 3(2): 251-253. Alaj, I. (2016). Université catholique de Louvain, Belgique.bn (Unpublished master degree). Kiriemadis, Th. & Theakou, E. (2007).SMIJ, 3(2), 27-37.

Sport Statistics and Analyses

DIFFERENCES IN METABOLIC AND ANTHROPOMETRIC PARAMETERS BETWEEN ATHLETES ON DIFFERENT TYPES OF TRAININGS

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Introduction: Resting metabolic rate (RMR) is a rate of energy which body needs in order to perform the basic functions such as breathing, circulation of the blood, brain functions and others, while it is in complete resting. It is approximately equal to basal metabolism. RMR is influenced by many factors, and

one of the greatest influences are body composition and hormonal influences. The goal of the study was to determine anthropometric and metabolic parameters of athletes engaged in different types of training, to compare obtained results and to examine whether there are statistically significant differences among them. Material and methods: The study included 42 male athletes divided into two groups. The first group consisted of 21 athletes who were predominantly performing aerobic type of training, and the other group consisted of 21 athletes performing anaerobic type of training. Anthropometric test (body weight, body height, skinfold thicknesses and circumferences) and RMR (using the indirect calorimetry method) were performed. The results were statistically analyzed and the differences in parameters between the two groups of athletes were compared. Results: There were statistically significant differences in body weight, amount of fat free mass (FFM) and muscle mass, body mass index, as well as in the relative metabolic parameters between two groups of subjects. Discussion: The greatest impact on RMR has a percentage of body weight that does not contain fat, i.e. FFM. The rate of metabolic activity of this body compartment is higher in athletes in aerobic than athletes in anaerobic type of training. References: Guyton A, Hall J. Textbook of medical physiology, eleventh edition. University of Mississippi; 2011. Harris JA, Benedict FG. A biometric study of human basal metabolism. Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 1918; 4(12):370-3. Illner K, Brinkmann G, Heller M, Bosy-Westphal A, Muller JM. Metabolically active components of fat free mass and resting energy expenditure in nonobese adults. Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab. 2000; 278(2):E308-15. Grujic N. Fiziologija sporta. Novi Sad:Futura; 2004. Srdic B, Stokic E, Polzovic A. Odnos parametara koji definišu velicinu i raspored masnog tkiva. Med Pregl. 2003; 5:232-6.

Sport Tourism

SUSTAINABLE SPORT HUNTING TOURISM IN NEWFOUNDLAND & LABRADOR: FOCUS ON THE MOOSE

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Introduction: The purpose of this paper is to highlight the impacts of sport hunting tourism with a focus on the moose in Newfoundland and Labrador Province in Canada. The study looks into the history of the moose, highlights economic impacts of hunting moose, the community impacts as well sustainability issues with regards to sport hunting. Methods: In this study, a case study approach was adopted to understand the sustainability of moose hunting as well as the economic impact in the Province. Competitive analysis of hunting tourism is considered. A case study approach enabled me to explore the issues emerging from moose hunting as a conservation tool and how it can contribute to community tourism development. Results: The results show there are economic benefits as well as some negative impact with regards to moose management. Various strategies can be utilized however, to manage any potential negative impacts in the future as well as manage moose populations sustainably, further resources need to be put in place. Discussion: The current literature highlights the much needed information on moose hunting as a sport in Newfoundland and Labrador. The benefits of sport hunting are also explored as well as community involvement in sustainable hunting practices. References: Bauer, H., Chapron, G., Nowell, K., Henschel, P., Funston, P. J., Hunter, L.T. B., & Packer, C. (2015). Lion (*Panthera leo*) populations are declining rapidly across Africa, except in intensively managed areas. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences United States of America, 112, 14894–14899. Begg, C.M., Miller, J.R.B., & Begg, K.S. (2017) Effective implementation of age restrictions increases selectivity of sport hunting of the African